

BASIC ASPECTS OF VOICE SUBSTITUTIONS IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATSIYA

Har bir morfemaning ko'p variantlaridan birini chiqish shakli yoki boshlang'ich shakli sifatida ajratib ko'rsatish orqali morfofonologik tavsifni tizimli ravishda taqdim etish mumkin. Masalani shu tarzda qo'yish o'zgarishlarning dastlabki shakli va yo'nalishini aniqlash muammosini hal etish yo'lini yoritib berishi mumkin. Ushbu muammo maqolada muhokama qilinadi. Hamma ovoz almashuvlari, jumladan, ma'no ifoda etmaydigan ovoz almashuvlari ham yo'naltirilgan hodisalar bo'lib, bu yo'nalish almashishning chap a'zosidan o'ng a'zosiga yo'naltiriladi. Har qanday ikkita lingvistik elementdan tashkil topgan almashirishning chap va o'ng a'zolari o'rtasidagi farq muhim belgi vazifasini bajaradi va almashirishda namoyon bo'ladigan o'zgarish yo'nalishini ko'rsatadi. Transformatsiya jarayonining boshlanishi chap a'zo bilan bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, chap a'zo chiqish shakli yoki boshlang'ich shakl deb hisoblanadi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

variatsiya, fonema, morfonologiya, tovush o'rnini bosish, fonologiya

АННОТАЦИЯ

Выделяя один из многих вариантов каждой морфемы как выходную или исходную форму, можно систематически представить морфонологическое описание. Такая постановка вопроса может пролить свет на решение проблемы определения исходной формы и направления изменений. Эта проблема обсуждается в статье. Все голосовые замены, в том числе и голосовые замены, не выражающие смысла, являются направленными событиями, и это направление направлено от левого члена замены к правому. Различие между левым и правым членами замены, состоящей из любых двух языковых элементов, выступает важным признаком и указывает на направление изменения, проявляющегося при замене. Поскольку начало процесса преобразования связано с левым элементом, левый элемент рассматривается как выходная форма или начальная форма.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

морфонология, замена звука, вариация, фонема, фонология, морфология.

ABSTRACT

By distinguishing one of the many variants of each morpheme as an output form or an initial form, a morpho-phonological description can be systematically presented. Putting the issue in this way can shed light on the solution to the problem of determining the initial form and direction of change. This problem is discussed in the article. All voice substitutions, including voice substitutions that do not express meaning, are directed events, and this direction is directed from the left member to the right member of the substitution. The difference between the left and right members of a substitution consisting of any two linguistic elements acts as an important feature and indicates the direction of the change manifested in the substitution. Since the beginning of the transformation process is related to the left member, the left member is considered as the output form or initial form.

KEY WORDS

variation, phoneme, morphonology, sound replacement, phonology

Introduction

Relevance of the topic and degree of development. Although there has been a clear revival of interest in the study of sound substitutions in various related and non-related languages in recent decades, the lack of development of several issues of the theory of alternation and the lack of comprehensive, typologically oriented descriptive studies in which the relations of substitution in specific languages are studied are insufficient for this promising field of linguistic typology. The research works carried out in this direction which include the presentation of the theory of alternation for certain language families or their certain groups of languages, and the alternation model or models based on it, aim to help eliminate that problem and become relevant. The idea that the language system is not a collection of elements and mechanisms of a homogeneous typological essence is considered a consideration that has been accepted almost unanimously since the time of the research of V. Humboldt, who is considered the founder of modern linguistic typology training, and in a certain sense, has gained the status of dogma. However, the typological nature of the components that make up this (polytopological) system, their mutual relationship (those components), the “consensus programs” created to achieve the coexistence of elements of different (typological) nature, the mechanism of “behavior” exhibited by the components with such characteristics in the conditions of polytopology and its many problems, such as the limit determined by the system, as well as the question of the “power ratio” of typological trends in the structural core of the system formed by elements and mechanisms of a different typological nature, are the “Achilles” of the various typological theories that have made important contributions in the history of linguistic thought. So, in linguistic typology, even the issues such as the concept of “language type” itself, which constitutes the core of this teaching, the reason for its formation, and what quantity and features it has based on the criteria of division, have not been resolved. - could not help the emergence of a series of problems.

Since it is necessary to form a typological inventory for the typological classification of world languages, it is important to define all manifestations of languages, including the typological, universal features of sound substitutions, and include them in this inventory, and in this regard, the topic of the research is relevant.

That sound or phoneme substitutions occur within a certain morpheme that represents a higher level in the language. In the substitutions that occur within the segmental units of the language, that is, the phonetic inventory, in other words, in phonetic substitutions, allophones of one sound or phoneme, which exclude each other in different phonetic positions, enter into substitution (alternation) relations. Because phonetic substitutions are always related to position, they appear as positional substitutions and combinatorial substitutions. Positional substitutions are determined by the place they occupy about the accent or word boundary, and combinatorial sound substitutions are determined by the presence of other sounds in the surroundings of the sound. Substitution relations are also possible between suprasegmental units such as tone and stress. Although sound substitutions are studied in various degrees from the aspect of positional substitutions and combinatorial substitutions in different languages, they have not been studied in Azerbaijani linguistics as a special object of contrastive/confrontational research based on the materials of a large number of languages with different systems. From this point of view, the issue raised in the dissertation is new and relevant. Although sound substitutions are studied in various degrees from the aspect of positional substitutions and combinatorial substitutions in different languages, they have not been studied in Azerbaijani linguistics as a special object of contrastive/confrontational research based on the materials of a large number of languages with different systems. From this point of view, the issue raised in the dissertation is new and relevant.

Metathetic shifts can be related to different levels of the language, that is, at the phonetic level, sounds or phonemes can be shifted under the influence of phonetic laws and events, and in the morphological layer, changes in the form of individual words can occur in the process of language development. As a result of the historical development of the languages of the world, the phenomenon of adaptation between the forms of language units can be realized by various phonetic changes, but also by morphonological changes, that is, ringing, deafening, lipping, aspiration, and other phenomena are related to the tendency of language units to settle and adapt in the process of development. Among those events, there is a shift in the structural arrangement of language units, in other words, metathesis. The phenomenon of adaptation resulting in displacement or metathesis also creates conditions for phonotactically arranging language units. According to the researcher, metatheses in the morphonological sense are not just the displacement of phonemes, but also the fact that this phoneme displacement accompanies the synchronous state of morphological events. From this point of view, metathesis can be defined as follows: a sound substitution can be considered a metathetic substitution when the right member of the substitution occurs through the displacement of the left member. In other words, the right member of a metathetic substitution consists of the same phonemes as its left member arranged in a different order. Sound substitutions are not only the main part of the phonological system of the language, but also the basis of the substitution relations, which are characteristic of the vocabulary of different languages, and play an important role in the word change and word creation processes. In those processes, sound substitutions, which appear as morphological means, are linguistic formal means and are used to express a certain morphological (no)logical meaning in different languages. Here, it is necessary to take into account the relevant rules of linguistic divisions such as phonetics, phonology, morphonology, and morphology. Issues related to the types of morpheme changes, their conditioning features, and functions are of great importance in the word formation and word change system of the language. There is an inverse relationship between the agglutination index and the number of morphemes that have been morphologically changed-Azerbaijani, Turkic, English, German, Tatar, etc. Sound substitutions, which appear as morphological means in

different languages, are linguistic formal means and are used to express a certain morphological meaning. Meaning, including morphological meaning, is necessarily either the signified or part of the signified. A means of expression, including a morphological means of expression, need not always be part of the signifier or the signified. Every language has meaningless, non-meaningful, or empty formal (expression) device(s) that have no signifier. For example, operations that are often found in the framework of morphology and do not have meaning, and do not express, as well as the order or sequence of morphological signs can be considered as such. The main types of morphological means are determined based on the anatomical and physiological nature of natural language, that is, its articulatory and acoustic properties. Those types are distinguished as essences, operations, and linear sequences. Essences are explained as discrete units perceived as essences in themselves. Operations are manipulations applied to essences. The linear sequence refers to the essences, it shows the sequence of their arrangement. In the flow of speech, sounds form larger units - syllables - and syllables, in turn, combine into word forms, then beats, phrases, and phrases. These units are located one after the other in the speech chain, they are arranged, therefore they are called linear or segmental units. Here the word “segment” needs an explanation. If we look at the explanation of the word “segment” in the linguistic literature, we notice that the degree of similarity of the given explanations is very close.

Linear or segmental language units are a certain part, section, or segment of a voiced speech or speech flow, i.e. sounds or their combinations that can be arranged in certain rows or lines. According to Matusevic, “linear units mean the sounds of the language that are arranged one after the other or their combinations”. Linear units are usually sounds/phonemes, syllables, morphemes, word combinations, etc. is attributed. The segmental units that form the basis of speech flow are divided into vowel and consonant sounds. Noting that there is an important articulation difference between vowel and consonant sounds, H. Hasanov explains that difference concerning V.A. Bogoroditsky: “... vowels have the function of opening the mouth, and consonants have the function of closing the mouth. The more we try to pronounce the vowel sounds out loud, the more we have to open the mouth, on the contrary, if we gradually pronounce the consonants out loud, we close the oral cavity more strictly” [Matusevich 1976].

Segmental sound substitutions the classification proposed by I. Melchuk is distinguished by its comprehensiveness. It is this classification that covers segmental sound substitutions as a whole. Based on that classification, it can be seen that any sound replacement in the world's languages belongs to one of the four main groups (substitutions, shortenings, expansions, and metathetic sound replacements). If we accept that the main aspect of morphonology is the phonological variability of morphemes, then attention should be paid to determining the direction of that variability. In other words, choosing the main variant of the morpheme turns out to be an important issue. It should be noted that L. Bloomfield, one of the founders of descriptive linguistics, made one of the first attempts to stratify morpheme variants on the material of the language, and distinguished one of the morphs as the main one [Kasevich 1986].

In order not to confuse the “metatheses” in the classification with the same phenomenon that occurs in phonetic sound substitutions, we will call them “metathetic sound substitutions”. Substitutions are considered one of the four main types of segmental sound substitutions. The term “substitution” has different meanings. O. Akhmanova explains the term “substitution” in two ways: “In descriptive linguistics, the similarities and differences of language units, their combination in classes (groups), their functional characteristics, etc. is the basic method of determining through mutual substitution in a set of contexts. The researcher mentions the

substitution method and phonetic substitution term combinations for that meaning. Let's pay attention to the second meaning explained by him: “Interrelationship of options in the expression plan; It is such a relationship or ratio between two elements of the signifier (expression) that replacing one with the other does not cause corresponding changes in the content signified by those elements...” [Akhmanova 1969]. Determining the direction of substitutions is important. For any pair of allomorphs, the determination of orientation leads to the selection of one of them as the original form, and the description of the second as derived from the first with some transformations. The issue of what criteria should be followed when determining the direction of replacements is also quite complicated. V. A. Plungyan notes that there are only two main criteria in that matter: “... a) if the distribution of allomorphs is described in such a way that the allomorph X appears in certain contexts K1, K2, ..., Kn, and the allomorph Y appears in all other contexts, then the Y allomorph is considered as the primary form...; b) the direction of substitutions is determined by the principle of “more diversity to less diversity” (in other words, if the rule requires that the phonemes x, y and z in the allomorphs be replaced by a phoneme w, then the allomorph containing w cannot be considered as an initial form” [Plungyan 2003] He, for example, ходит “to walk” ~ хожу “I walk” и возит “to carry (with a car)” ~ вожу “I carry (with a car)” indicates that the initial form is given first.

When a morpheme is represented by several variants, I noted that criteria are needed that allow one of them to be accepted as the initial form and to determine the direction of change in different variants. Melchuk sees the solution to this in the following way: “If the observed phoneme relations are in the form of additional distribution of their members (phonological or morphological) relative to the context, the direction of the corresponding substitutions should be chosen in such a way that this distribution is described as simply as possible” [Melchuk 2000]. The researcher considers this principle as a general tendency, an initiative for the maximum simplicity of the description. It is in Russian *кóс + ит / кáш + ива (+л)*, *нос + ит / нáш + ива (+л)*, *спрос+ ит / спрáш+ива (+л)*, *лов + ит / лáвл + ива (+л)*, *въллов+ит / вылáвл+ива (+л)*, *брод + ит / брáж+ ива (+л)*, *хóд + ить / хáж+ива (+л)*, *сход+ит / схáж+ива (+л)* and etc. shows the existence of many pairs of verbs.

Here, /o/ is substituted, and /á/ is substituted. | and the one after the sign is the context or condition that makes the substitution /o/ => /á/ possible. In the mentioned verbs, /á/ is used only before the suffix -ива, while /o/ appears in all other positions. Choosing the opposite direction of substitution, i.e. /á/ => /o/, firstly, would be a denial of the previous condition, and secondly, would make the definition of the new condition more complicated from a formal point of view. In other words, it would be very difficult to list all the contexts and conditions that determine the transition of /á/ to /o/. Therefore, the condition of having /o/ in the examples mentioned above is more limited. For this reason, the forms with /o/ are selected as the initial form in those examples.

The principle of “less complex condition” (принцип наименее сложного участъ) [Melchuk 2000] is considered a crucial step in determining the direction of substitutions and the selection of the initial form. I. Melchuk emphasizes the importance of paying attention to three aspects of complexity: 1) logical complexity (negation is considered to be more complex than the corresponding affirmation); 2) qualitative complexity (it is assumed that the morphological condition is more complex than the phonological one); 3) quantitative complexity (the number of constraints is considered here) [Melchuk 2000]. According to its essence, the principle of “less complex condition” can also be called the principle of “diversity to sameness”. The rationale here is that defining the direction of substitution in this way confirms that different segments overlap

within a given context or condition, otherwise, it would not be easy to explain the transition of one segment to different segments in the same context. In the analysis of substitutions, it is important to consider two directions of their development - convergent and divergent.

Result

In different languages, due to the influence of the vowels in the root of the word, the change of vowels in the suffixes, synchronism is manifested. In this case, we are talking about apical harmony. Affixal harmony is a very common phenomenon in the languages of the world, but it is the root of the word that triggers such harmony. In Turkic, Finno-Ugric, Mongolian, and Tungus-Manchu languages, the dominant morpheme is the word root, and the suffixes are suffixes.

For example:

Azerbaijani language: -s, -s: at+s, ev+s;

Turkish language: -lar, -ler: at+lar, ev+ler;

Gagauz language: -lar/-lär, (-nar/-när): kiät+lär, üzük+lär, alksin+nar, gelsin+när [Pokrovskaya 1997].

Kazakh language: -lar/-ler, -tar/-ter, -dar/-der [Kaydarov 1997].

Bashkir language: -lar/-s, -tar/-tar, -dar/-dar, -zar/ -zar [Kazimov 2019].

As can be seen from the examples, all allomorphs of the plural form are conditioned to the same extent by root vocalism, and none of them can be considered as an initial form. In such a case, the direction of substitutions shown for the listed Turkic languages cannot be determined, and such substitutions are considered non-directional substitutions. The most appropriate way to represent such substitutions may be to mark the vowels in the substitution series with generalization symbols. For example, the suffix -lar/-s can be marked as /IVr/, and its other variations, i.e. -dar/-der – dVr, нар/-нär - /nVr/, -tar/-тер – tVr, зар/-зәр – It can be denoted by generalizing symbols in the form zVr, where the symbol V denotes a variable vowel. Such substitutions without direction are possible in auxiliary morphemes, but their possibility in root morphemes is doubtful.

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